

ESTIMATION OF WEATHERABILITY FLEXURAL PROPERTIES FOR CFRP SUBJECTED TO LONG-TERM OUTDOOR EXPOSURE

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Abstract

The present paper discusses the degradation mechanism for weatherability flexural properties of CFRP subjected to outdoor and accelerated exposures. One of the specimens was made of epoxy resin and unidirectional carbon fiber prepregs having the fiber orientation angles of 0 or 90 degree and another specimen was made of the same epoxy resin only as the matrix of the prepregs. In order to clarify the effects of exposure period on the variations of flexural strengths and moduli, matrix volume fractions, thickness and absorption rate of infrared rays, the complex accelerated exposure test was conducted to continue for up 100 cycles and a direct outdoor exposure has been also conducted to continue for 156 months. It was shown that both the weatherability flexural strengths had been calculated by results of epoxy resin and thickness change of CFRP during the exposures. The experimental values of flexural strength could be estimated on the data of outdoor exposure until the 36 months and on the data of accelerated exposure until the 16 cycles. Furthermore, the correlation of the acceleration exposure test to the outdoor ones was demonstrated.

1 Introduction

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) are utilized in various structures because they have such as specific strength, specific rigidity and corrosion resistance. In a wider range of structural applications of CFRP, the materials exposed to complex environmental effects and these effects cause a degradation of CFRP. If weatherability properties

can be predicted, the durability and reliability of CFRP can be improved. It was known in the past papers [1] that the multiple effects of ultraviolet radiation from the solar light, moisture absorption and hydrochloric acid absorption decreased the strength of GFRP subjected to the outdoor exposure. Specifically, the standing out of fibers owing to the reduction of surface resin was reported in GFRP [2] and in CFRP [3], [4]. According to the increase of the outdoor exposure period, this phenomenon was often observed and it seemed to be a cause of the strength degradation in both FRP's. On the other hand, the strength in the fiber direction in CFRP mainly depended on the fiber strength and the fiber volume fraction, and it seemed to exhibit no effect of outdoor exposure. However, it should be made clear whether the degradation of epoxy resin caused by outdoor exposure had an effect on the strength of unidirectional CFRP or not. Since the outdoor exposure test needs long periods to evaluate test [5,6].

Aiming at the effects of ultraviolet radiation from solar light, moisture absorption and hydrochloric acid absorption on the degradation of weatherability strength of CFRP, this paper presents the flexural properties of CFRP subjected to outdoor and accelerated exposure. We used two classes of specimens. The first class of specimens is two unidirectional CFRP laminates having different fiber orientation angles 0 or 90 degree, respectively. The second class of specimens is made solely of epoxy resin identical in chemical composition to the matrix of the above CFRP laminates. In order to clarify the effects of exposure period on the variation of flexural strength and modulus, matrix volume

fraction, thickness and absorption rate of infrared ray, the complex accelerated exposure test was conducted to continue for up 100 cycles and a direct outdoor exposure has been also conducted to continue for 156 months. It was shown that both the weatherability flexural strengths have been calculated by results of epoxy resin and thickness change of CFRP during the exposures. The experimental values of flexural strength could be estimated on the data of outdoor exposure until the 36 months and on the data of accelerated exposure until the 16 cycles. Furthermore, the correlation of the acceleration exposure test to the outdoor ones was demonstrated.

2 Experimental methods

2.1 Specimens

Table 1 showed the composition and dimension of CFRP and epoxy resin plates for the both of exposure tests. After finishing the designated exposure period, four sides of the test plates were cut off 6 mm from their edges to avoid the 5 specimens as shown in Figure 1. By using these 5 specimens, the experimental values of flexural strength and modulus, thickness, matrix volume fraction and absorption rate of infrared rays were obtained for the designated periods including the beginning of both of the exposures. Hereafter, the specimens are referred as CF0, CF90 and EP, respectively, for shortness.

2.2 Exposure test

In order to closely simulate the outdoor exposure environment, the accelerated exposure test was executed by the following three stages, namely, a sunshine weather test, a salt spray test and holding at

Fig.1 Test plate and flexural specimens

Table 2 Conditions of accelerated exposure test of a cycle

Sunshine Weather Test	Black panel temperature [°C]	63 ± 3
	Ultraviolet rays period [h]	100
	Water spray period [h]	15
	Test period [h]	100
	Accumulative dose [MJ/m ²]	28
Salt Spray Test	Salt concentration [%]	5 ± 1
	Temperature [°C]	35 ± 2
	pH-value	5.6 ~ 6.0
	Test period [h]	24
Standard Condition	Temperature [°C]	23 ± 2
	Humidity [%]	50 ± 5
	Test period [h]	44

Table 1 Three kinds of specimens

	CF0	CF90	EP
Reinforcement	Unidirectional carbon fiber PAN type		—
	[0] ₈	[90] ₈	
Matrix	Epoxy of bisphenol A type		
Size (mm)	150 × 70 × 1.0		150 × 70 × 2.0

Fig.2 Outdoor exposure in Japan Weathering Test Center at Choshi-city

room temperature. There were conducted to condition of accelerated exposure test as shown in Table 2. The total of 168 hours in the three stages was determined to be one cycle and the longest exposure period was 100 cycles. As for the outdoor exposure test, plates were installed on the weathering rack that was located at an area near sea in Choshi City and was shown in Figure 2. This exposure test had continued since February 1996 to 2009. The plates were sampled at every 6 months from start of experiment to 5 years and every 12 months from 6 years to 13 years, respectively.

2.3 Evaluative procedures

First, thickness of five specimens expired the designated exposure period was measured at three positions of each specimen and their average values were to be used in the following discussion. Next, these specimens were tested by a four point bending test in order to get the flexural strengths and modulus for the designated exposure period. Then,

the bending specimen was cut into small pieces for measuring the matrix volume fraction. By using a method of FTIR, the outer (surface) and inner layer of the matrix in CFRP was analyzed and the deterioration degree of the resin was distinguished measuring to the methylene radical of absorption rate of infrared rays subjected to the exposure. Furthermore, it was thought that this variation might explain the relation of the flexural strength.

3 Experimental results

3.1 Results of CFRP

$S_{\theta,0}$ ($\theta=0,90$) was the average values of flexural strength for the initial period of CF0 and CF90 for outdoor exposure test. ($S_{\theta,i}/S_{\theta,0}$) were the ratios of exposure period and they were shown for the outdoor exposure month period (X_m) in Figure 3 (a). In this figure, the flexural strength ratio of the CF0 specimens decreased slightly and its value was

(a) Outdoor exposure

(a) Outdoor exposure

(b) Accelerated exposure

(b) Accelerated exposure

Fig.3 Results of flexural strength ratios under outdoor and accelerated exposure for CF0 and 90

Fig.4 Results of flexural modulus ratios under outdoor and accelerated exposure for CF0 and 90

within 1.2 % at the 156 months of the outdoor exposure test. Since the coefficient variance of flexural strength ratio was 4.0% for the initial property, the strength ratio of the CF0 decreased within the initial scatter of flexural strength and exposure of long-term periods hardly affected the strength of the CF0 specimens. The flexural strength ratio of the CF90 decreased with the increase of the exposure period and their values were 14% at the 156 months of the outdoor exposure. It was over the initial scatter (C.V of initial flexural strength ratio = 2.5%) and it was sufficiently large to be able to recognize the effect of exposure. The flexural strength ratios were shown for the accelerated cycle period (X_c) in Figure 3 (b). The CF0 specimens decreased 3 % at 100 cycles of the accelerated exposure test. The flexural strength ratio of the CF90 decreased 14.8 % at the 100 cycles. From these two lines of the CF0 in Fig.3 (a) and (b), one year's exposure in the outdoor test was equivalent to 4.8 cycles in the accelerated test. The CF90 was equivalent to 5.2 cycles per year. In the previous paper [4], the CF0 was 5.4 cycles per year and the

(a) Outdoor exposure

(b) Accelerated exposure

Fig.6 Results of thickness ratios under outdoor and accelerated exposure for CF0 and 90

(a) Outdoor exposure

(b) Accelerated exposure

Fig.5 Results of matrix volume fraction ratios under outdoor and accelerated exposure for CF0 and 90

(a) Outdoor exposure

(b) Accelerated exposure

Fig.7 Results of degraded depth in surface under outdoor and accelerated exposure for CF0 and 90

CF90 was 5.1 cycles per year. The values of correlation were in agreement with the CF0 and the CF90 in short and long-term exposures. Figure 4 were shown a similar reduction in the flexural modulus ratio ($E_{0,i}/E_{0,0}$) to one of the strength ratio. The ratio of matrix volume fractions ($V_{m0,i}/V_{m0,0}$) similarly decreased as the strength ratios in Figure 5 along of the reduction on the surface region by the ultraviolet radiation from the solar light. Figure 6 presented a slight reduction of thickness ratio ($t_{0,i}/t_{0,0}$) and this phenomenon was called the slenderness of matrix. In Figure 7, the degraded depth in surface ($t_{d0,i}$) were shown the increasing tendency and their values were about 0.20 mm at 156 months in the outdoor exposure test and about 0.25 mm at 100 cycles in the accelerated test. These absorption rates implied the deterioration of matrix resin owing to the exposures. Therefore, the deterioration of matrix resin and the slenderness of matrix resin caused the reduction of flexural strength in the CF90 specimens but they did not affect the flexural strength of CF0 because its strength mainly depends absorption rate of the infrared rays in matrix on fiber's strength.

3.2 Results of epoxy resin

Figure 8 shows the results of the flexural strength ratio ($S_{m,i}/S_{m,0}$) of EP made of solely epoxy resin identical in chemical composition to the matrix of CFRP preregs under both exposures. The flexural strength ratio of EP decreased more than CF90. In the Figure 9, flexural modulus ratio ($E_{m,i}/E_{m,0}$) of EP were also decreased. In the correlation of both exposures, one year's outdoor exposure is equivalent to about 5.3~5.6 cycles in the accelerated exposure.

4 Comparisons of strength ratio of 144 and 156 months with calculated ones

The calculated flexural strength ratios could be obtained by used of their data from 36 months and 16 cycles [4]. Then, the flexural strength ratios of 144 and 156 months in the outdoor exposure were compared with the calculated ones in Figure 10. In the cases of the CF0 and the CF90, the calculated

Fig.8 Results of flexural strength ratio under outdoor and accelerated exposure for epoxy resin

Fig.9 Results of flexural modulus ratios under outdoor and accelerated exposure for epoxy resin

Fig.10 Comparison of experimental flexural strength ratio at 12 and 13 years with estimated ones from the first accelerated 16 cycles and outdoor 36 months exposures

flexural strength ratios depended on the data of outdoor exposure test until the 36 months and on the data of accelerated exposure test until the 16 cycles showed an excellent accordance with those of outdoor experiment test data at the 144 and 156 months.

5 Conclusions

In order to investigate the weatherability flexural strength ratios of the CFRP laminates, two kinds of unidirectional CFRP laminates and only epoxy resin identical composition to the matrix of the CFRP specimens under the outdoor exposure and accelerated exposure were examined. Weatherability flexural strength ratios of the 144 and 156 months could be estimated.

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